

On lapped splices in high-strength steels - Experimental investigations and damage-mechanical simulations

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ABSTRACT

High-strength steel has a lot of advantages compared to conventional-strength steel. Its incredible strength, durability and adaptability have engineers reimagining what's possible. With its use, cross-section dimensions can be reduced to a minimum, thus material gets saved and transport effort is reduced. Consequently, using high-strength steel has a positive influence on the carbon footprint of steel constructions. Steel in general also has a high potential regarding reusability. To create flexible and reusable structures, bolted connections are necessary. In the European standards, lapped splices or bolted connections are regulated in EN 1993-1-8 and its current revision prEN 1993-1-8, which were developed for steel grades up to S460. In order to verify the design rules also for high-strength steels and to maximize the potential of bolted joints, experimental and numerical investigations on bolted connections for high-strength steel plates had been performed.

The paper represents the key findings of the investigations on lapped splices (with one bolt) using two different high-strength steels, S690QL and S700MC. Especially the geometrical parameters, like edge distances, have been varied. In all cases, bolts were chosen, so that failure occurred in the plates and not the bolt itself. The two typical failure modes, bearing and net cross-section failure, were provoked. Based on the results of the experimental investigations with additional small-scale-tests, e.g. round bar and Charpy tests, numerical models could be calibrated using damage-mechanical models, in detail the modified Bai-Wierzbicki damage model. With the calibrated models it is possible to simulate the experimental tests including failure. The aim of the investigations is the review of current design rules, the identification optimization potential and to expand the standards for the application of high-strength steels.

Keywords: High-strength steel, Lapped splices, Bolted connections, Design

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the use of high-strength steel allows to reduce cross-section dimensions in steel construction. By saving material and resources also the transportation requirements are reduced and thus, high-strength steel contributes to more sustainable structures. Additionally, bolted connections, such as in lapped splices, allow to construct demountable and therefore also reusable constructions, which can save a lot of carbon emissions in the future. The design of these connections is defined in EN 1993-1-8 (1) and its current revision prEN 1993-1-8 (2). These standards were developed for steel grades up to S460. That is why the validity of these rules will be evaluated within this paper based on experimental investigations. Furthermore, numerical models have been developed using a damage-mechanical concept to simulate these experiments using finite element methods. This allows to investigate the load bearing behaviour of any geometry including failure with numerical methods.

2 STATE-OF-THE-ART REGARDING STANDARDISATION

When designing lapped splices, different verifications have to be done to ensure that neither bearing failure nor net cross-section failure will occur. In the European Union, the Eurocode 3 (3) provides design rules for steel structures. Bolted connections, as for lapped splices, are regulated in EN 1993-1-8 (1). In the current revision of the standards, some changes regarding the design of lapped splices or bolted connections have been made in prEN 1993-1-8 (2). In the following, the verifications for bearing failure, gross and net cross-section failure of EN 1993-1-8 (1) and prEN 1993-1-8 (2) will be presented.

Fig. 1 Definition of edge- and hole-spacings acc. to prEN 1993-1-8 (2)

Therefore, Fig. 1 defines the edge- and hole-spacings, used also for the verifications, of prEN 1993-1-8 (2). There are also limits for minimum and maximum spacings.

Gross cross-section resistance

The resistance $N_{pl,Rd}$ of the gross cross-section is calculated with Eq. (1) in the undisturbed area acc. to EN 1993-1-8 (1) and prEN 1993-1-8 (2).

$$N_{pl,Rd} = \frac{A_{gross} \cdot f_y}{\gamma_{M0}} \quad (1)$$

with

A_{gross}	Gross cross-section in undisturbed area
f_y	Yield strength
γ_{M0}	Partial safety factor (=1,00)

Net cross-section resistance

Details with a disturbed cross-section, e.g. due to holes, must have a sufficient load-bearing capacity of the net cross-section $N_{u,Rd}$. Different crack lines can lead to a failure of the net cross-section, Fig. 2. For possible net cross-sections, the verification acc. to EN 1993-1-8 (1) is:

Possible crack lines for A_{net}

a) 1-2-3-4-5

b) 1-2-4-5

Fig. 2 Possible crack lines for net cross-section failure

$$N_{u,Rd} = \frac{0.9 \cdot A_{net} \cdot f_u}{\gamma_{M2}} \quad (2)$$

with

A_{net}	Net cross-section (acc. to Fig. 2)
f_u	Tensile strength
γ_{M2}	Partial safety factor (=1,25)

The factor 0.9 has been replaced in prEN 1993-1-8 (2) by the factor k as follows:

$$N_{u,Rd} = \frac{k \cdot A_{net} \cdot f_u}{\gamma_{M2}} \quad (3)$$

with

$k = 1,0$ for cross-sections with smooth holes (e.g. by water jet cutting)

$k = 0,9$ for cross-sections with rough holes (e.g. by flame cutting)

$k = 0,9$ for details that are subjected to fatigue

Bearing resistance

The bearing resistance $F_{b,Rd}$, as given in EN 1993-1-8 (1), is defined by Eq. (4), where coefficients that take into account the edge and hole spacings were considered.

$$F_{b,Rd} = \frac{k_1 \cdot \alpha_b \cdot f_u \cdot d \cdot t}{\gamma_{M2}} \quad (4)$$

with

d Shank diameter of the bolt

t Plate thickness

α_b, k_1 Coefficients in and transverse to the direction of force acc. to Tab. 1

The coefficients are summarized in Tab. 1.

Tab. 1 Coefficients α_b and k_1 for the hole bearing resistance acc. to EN 1993-1-8 (1)

	in the direction of load transfer	perpendicular to the direction of load transfer
for end bolts	$a_b = \min \left\{ \frac{e_1}{3d_0}, \frac{f_{ub}}{f_u}; 1.0 \right\}$	$k_1 = \min \left\{ 2.8 \frac{e_2}{d_0} - 1.7; 1.4 \frac{p_2}{d_0} - 1.7; 2.5 \right\}$
for inner bolts	$a_b = \min \left\{ \frac{p_1}{3d_0} - \frac{1}{4}, \frac{f_{ub}}{f_u}; 1.0 \right\}$	$k_1 = \min \left\{ 1.4 \frac{p_2}{d_0} - 1.7; 2.5 \right\}$
with		
e_1, e_2, p_1, p_2	Edge and hole spacings acc. to Fig. 1	
f_{ub}	Tensile strength of the bolt material	

In prEN 1993-1-8 (2), the factor k_1 is replaced by the factor k_m , which considers the steel grade of the plates, Eq. (5). The definition of the coefficient α_b has also slightly changed, Tab. 2.

$$F_{b,Rd} = \frac{k_m \cdot \alpha_b \cdot f_u \cdot d \cdot t}{\gamma_{M2}} \quad (5)$$

with

k_m Coefficient for bearing resistance (0.9 for steel grades $\geq$ S460, 1.0 else)

α_b Coefficient for bearing resistance acc. to Tab. 2

Tab. 2 Coefficients α_b for the hole bearing resistance acc. to prEN 1993-1-8 (2)

	in the direction of load transfer
for end bolts	$\alpha_b = \min\left\{\frac{e_1}{d_0}, 3\frac{f_{ub}}{f_u}; 3.0\right\}$
for inner bolts	$\alpha_b = \min\left\{\frac{p_1}{d_0} - \frac{1}{2}, 3\frac{f_{ub}}{f_u}; 3.0\right\}$
with	
e_1, e_2, p_1, p_2	Edge and hole spacings acc. to Fig. 1
f_{ub}	Tensile strength of the bolt material

For hole patterns with multiple bolts, block failure has to be checked in addition. There are also rules on the load bearing capacity of the bolts itself to prevent shear or tension failure of the bolts, but these will not be explained here, because the conducted experiments were all designed so that the failure of the bolts does not happen.

Additional rules for slightly different details, such as angles connected by one leg or pin ended members are also defined in EN 1993-1-8 (1) and prEN 1993-1-8 (2).

3 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS

3.1 Introduction

The specimens represent lapped splices and were designed using the rules of prEN 1993-1-8 (2) to investigate the different failure modes, esp. bearing and net cross-section failure, and check the design rules for high-strength steels. Specimens with one bolt (Detail LV_1.X) were investigated. All specimens were fabricated using water jet cutting. As a bolt, an M48 in 12.9 ($d_0 = 51$ mm) was used to exclude failure of the bolt. Two materials, an S690QL with a plate thickness of 20 mm and an S700MC with a thickness of 15 mm, were tested. The length of the bolt was chosen so that the shank is in the shear joint, Fig. 4 d). Each test has two outer plates and one inner plate (designed to fail).

3.2 Geometrical properties

The geometrical properties of the specimens investigated are summarized in Tab. 3.

Tab. 3 Geometrical properties of the investigated specimens (Detail LV_1.X)

Specimen	Number of bolts	Edge distance e_1		Edge distance e_2	
	[-]	[mm]	[d_0]	[mm]	[d_0]
LV_1.1	1	153	3.00	150	2.94
LV_1.2	1	61	1.20	150	2.94
LV_1.3	1	153	3.00	61	1.20
LV_1.4	1	61	1.20	61	1.20
LV_1.5	1	107	2.10	107	2.10
LV_1.6	1	107	2.10	150	2.94

3.3 Material properties

The material properties of the two tested high-strength steels S690QL and S700MC are summarized in Tab. 4. Both steels fulfil the ductility requirements of EN 1993-1-1 (4). In the stress-strain-diagram, the S690QL shows a pronounced yield strength with a yield plateau while the S700MC has none.

Tab. 4 Material properties of the used high-strength steels S690QL and S700MC

Material	Plate thickness	Yield strength R_{eH} or $R_{p0.2}$	Tensile strength R_m	Uniform elongation A_g	Failure strain A_x
	[mm]	[MPa]	[MPa]	[%]	[%]
S690QL	20	775	815	6.7	18.8
S700MC	15	880	1004	3.5	12.8

3.4 Test setup, execution and measurement

The specimens were tested in a 12 MN tensile test machine under pure tension. A schematic drawing of the tension test is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 Schematic test setup

The investigated detail is arranged in the middle. The two outer plates are hydraulically clamped (fixed) and the inner plate is clamped in a movable clamping. The load is applied as a horizontal displacement of the movable clamping, so of the inner plate.

Exemplarily, a test setup is shown in Fig. 4 a). To reduce the influence of

friction between the outer and the inner splicing plates, a distance between these is ensured using spacing plates at the clamping of the outer plates, Fig. 4 b) and c).

The tests were extensively equipped with measurement technology. In addition to piston force and piston travel, strain gauges and inductive displacement sensors were used. The displacement sensors were attached to the upper and bottom edge of the inner plate, as well as to the outer plates. Thus, the displacement sensors measure the relative deformation between the outer and inner plates, where the connection was always completely within the measuring range. The strain gauges were applied around the hole of the inner plate and in a neutral area.

Fig. 4 Test setup: a) and b) Exemplary installed specimen of detail LV_1, c) Clamping with lining plates and d) Length of the bolt shank

3.5 Test results

In the following, the main test results will be presented. The fracture images of the specimens are shown in Fig. 7. The maximum loads of all specimens as well as a comparison with the resistances acc. to EN 1993-1-8 (1) and prEN 1993-1-8 (2) are summarized in Tab. 5.

In general, the results, including fracture images and force-displacement-behaviour, were similar for the two investigated steel grades. Both typical failure modes, net cross-section failure and bearing failure, were observed.

The influence of the edge distance e_1 can be analysed with Fig. 5 (left). Here, the force-displacement-curves of specimen LV_1.1_S690 ($e_1=3.0 d_0$, $e_2=2.94 d_0$), LV_1.2_S690 ($e_1=1.2 d_0$, $e_2=2.94 d_0$), LV_1.3_S700 ($e_1=3.0 d_0$, $e_2=1.2 d_0$), and LV_1.4_S700 ($e_1=1.2 d_0$, $e_2=1.2 d_0$) are compared. Specimens LV_1.1_S690 and LV_1.2_S690 both showed bearing failure and differ only in the edge distance e_1 . The experimental load of LV_1.1_S690 is much higher than of LV_1.2_S690 (factor 2.21), which shows the significant influence of e_1 .

For the Specimens LV_1.3_S700 and LV_1.4_S700, the different edge distances e_1 lead to different failure modes. With a small edge distance e_1 (LV_1.4) bearing failure occurs, while for bigger edge distance (LV_1.3) the net cross-section fails, Fig. 7. The difference in the load maximum is small (factor 1.3) despite the switch of the failure modes.

Fig. 5 Force-displacement-curves for the tests LV_1.1_S690, LV_1.2_S690, LV_1.3_S700 and LV_1.4_S700 (left) and LV_1.5_S690 and LV_1.6_S690

The influence of the edge distance e_2 is seen in Fig. 5 (right) for the specimens LV_1.5_S690 ($e_1=2.1 d_0$, $e_2=2.1 d_0$) and LV_1.6_S690 ($e_1=2.1 d_0$, $e_2=2.94 d_0$). Both specimens failed due to bearing. A bigger edge distance e_2 has a positive effect on the maximum load. Thus, the influence of e_1 on the bearing load is much higher.

Exemplarily, the strain development of the specimen LV_1.1_S690 ($e_1=3.0 d_0$, $e_2=2.94 d_0$) is given in Fig. 6. Five strain gauges (SG) were attached to the specimen. SG-01 was applied in the pressure area behind the hole, that is why it develops high negative strains from the beginning. The measurement was limited by the maximum absorbable elongation of the SG, which is why SG-01 shows no more results after reaching around 17 % strain at a displacement of 7.6 mm. The strains in the tension area above the hole (SG-02) were relatively small (under 5 %). SG-04 and SG-05 were applied in the tension area behind the hole on the two outer plates to ensure, that these don't exhibit bearing failure and to measure a possible misalignment during the test. The results showed, that no misalignment occurred.

Fig. 6 Strain development for LV_1.1 made of S690QL

The comparison of the fracture images, Fig. 7, show clearly the two different failure modes. For the bearing failure it can be seen, that with bigger edge distances e_1 wedge-shaped failure gets more pronounced, compare fracture images of LV_1.1, LV_1.2 and LV_1.6.

Specimen	S690QL	S700MC
LV_1.1		
LV_1.2		
LV_1.3		
LV_1.4		
LV_1.5		
LV_1.6		

Fig. 7 Fracture images of the investigated specimens

Tab. 5 compares the experimental load F_{exp} with the resistances acc. to EN 1993-1-8 (1) and prEN 1993-1-8 (2). Here, for the calculation of the resistances $\gamma_{M2} = 1.25$ was changed to $\gamma_{M0} = 1.00$ due to the fact, that all material properties are known from laboratory tests. The design rules predict the correct failure mode and lead in all cases to conservative results. This demonstrates their applicability to high-strength steels. The rules acc. to prEN 1993-1-8 (2) provide for both failure modes more economical results. For the net cross-section resistance, no further optimization-potential can be derived based on the small number of test results with net cross-section failure. For the bearing resistance, it can be seen that especially for the specimens with small edge distances e_1 and e_2 ($< 2.1 d_0$), very conservative loads are predicted. Optimization potential for the bearing resistance acc. to prEN 1993-1-8 (2) can be found in the factor k_m and α_b . This should be further investigated, but it could be shown, that e.g. with a factor of $k_m = 0.98$ instead of 0.90 for steel grades $> S460$ and a minimum value of $\min(\alpha_b) = 2.8$ instead of 3.0, the bearing resistance can be predicted more economically.

Tab. 5 Comparison of the test results with the resistances acc. to EN 1993-1-8 (1) and prEN 1993-1-8 (2)

Test	Experimental load F_{exp} [kN]	EN 1993-1-8*			prEN 1993-1-8*		
		$N_{u,Rd}$	$F_{b,Rd}$	$F_{exp}/\min(N_{u,Rd}; F_{b,Rd})$	$N_{u,Rd}$	$F_{b,Rd}$	$F_{exp}/\min(N_{u,Rd}; F_{b,Rd})$
		[kN]	[kN]	[-]	[kN]	[kN]	[-]
LV_1.1_S690	2202	3653	1956	1,13	4059	2112	1,04
LV_1.1_S700	1987	3375	1807	1,10	3750	1952	1,02
LV_1.2_S690	996	3653	780	1,28	4059	842	1,18
LV_1.2_S700	911	3375	721	1,26	3750	778	1,17
LV_1.3_S690	1201	1042	1290	1,15	1157	2112	1,04
LV_1.3_S700	1152	962	1192	1,20	1069	1952	1,08
LV_1.4_S690	922	1042	514	1,79	1157	842	1,09
LV_1.4_S700	859	962	475	1,81	1069	778	1,10
LV_1.5_S690	1675	2391	1368	1,22	2657	1477	1,13
LV_1.5_S700	1538	2209	1264	1,22	2455	1365	1,13
LV_1.6_S690	1745	3653	1368	1,28	4059	1477	1,18
LV_1.6_S700	1589	3375	1264	1,26	3750	1365	1,16

* with $\gamma_{M0} = 1,00$ instead of $\gamma_{M2} = 1,25$ (known material properties)

decisive

4 DAMAGE MECHANICAL SIMULATIONS

The tests were also modelled numerically with damage-mechanical approaches, whose efficiency was already shown in (5) and (6). The geometry was modelled exactly as in the experiments. A Bai-Wierzbicki (7; 8) damage model, considering the stress state in terms of stress triaxiality and lode-angle, was implemented. The damage parameters were derived in (9) on laboratory scale using mostly smooth and notched round bar, shear, and Charpy tests.

Fig. 8 Numerical model including mesh (left) and comparison of experimental (F_{exp}) and numerical (F_{num}) loads (right)

Also, the mesh size influence (on plastic strains) was investigated in (9) to use the damage model with a mesh size of 2 mm, as used in the numerical models in the area of the bolts, Fig. 8 (left). The

Fig. 9 Experimental and numerical force-displacement-curves for LV_1.3_S690 and LV_1.5_S700

contact between bolt and plates was modelled with a friction coefficient of $\mu = 0.3$. The numerical models were calibrated extensively and validated against the experimental results. With the calibrated numerical models, the force-displacement-behaviour, Fig. 9, could be simulated tremendously satisfying. The ultimate loads of the experiments (F_{exp}) are also well predicted with the numerical simulations (F_{num}), Fig. 8 (right). They deviate less than 2 %. It can be highlighted that esp. for the different stress states for the different failure modes (bearing and net cross-section failure), the behaviour was represented realistically in the simulations. Also, the failure modes, Fig. 10, were correct and the different failure modes occur using one consistent material model with the derived damage parameters and considering the mesh size dependency as well as the calibrations of (9).

With the numerical methods developed, it is now feasible to comprehensively model lapped splices or bolt connections, encompassing failure mechanisms. Notably, these methods enable the accurate representation of different types of failure for various stress states for any geometry of lapped splices. The models can be used to carry out extensive verifications and optimizations of the design rules.

Fig. 10 Comparison of experimental and numerical failure modes: LV_1.2_S700 (left), LV_1.3_S690 (middle) and LV_1.4_S690 (right)

5 SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

The paper presents experimental and numerical investigations on lapped splices made of high-strength steel with one bolt. The specimens were designed to investigate all possible geometries for single bolt connections to provoke net cross-section and bearing failure. The experimental results showed both failure modes occurred. The main findings of this paper are:

1. The design rules of EN 1993-1-8 (1) and prEN 1993-1-8 (2) regarding lapped splices or bolted connections are applicable for high-strength steels.

2. The resistances based on prEN 1993-1-8 (2) are higher compared to the resistances based on EN 1993-1-8 (1) and thus, more economical.
3. Optimization potential for the bearing resistance acc. to. prEN 1993-1-8 (2) was found and a first optimization approach was presented.
4. Numerical models including damage-mechanical concepts could be calibrated and validated against the experimental results.
5. The results support the wider use of high-strength steels in steel construction and allows to design resource saving, demountable and therefore also reusable structures, which can save a lot of carbon emissions in the future.

With the developed numerical models, all possible geometries can be simulated including failure. This brings great potential to investigate further research questions. The next steps should be:

1. Investigation of lapped splices with multiple bolts to check the design rules for high-strength-steel for any possible geometry, esp. to focus on net cross-section failure.
2. Investigation of block tearing.
3. Investigation of other details like angles connected by one leg or pin ended members.
4. Development of rules on numerical simulations for designing steel structures, e.g. for implementation in prEN 1993-1-14 (10).

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